

**DEVELOPING FMCG BRAND USING MARKETING COMMUNICATION
TOOLS – A CONCEPTUAL STUDY**

Mr. Soumya Mukherjee,
Assistant Professor,
Bengal School of Technology & Management,
Chinsura, Hooghly
&
Dr. Mrinal Kanti Das
Assistant Professor and Teacher-In-Charge,
Centre for Management Studies,
JIS College of Engineering, Kalyani, Nadia

Abstract

Now-a-days, markets have taken a different dimension owing to the overpopulation of both large and small companies. As a result, markets have become overcrowded with many marketing messages. This has altogether make it quite difficult for the customers to perceive the marketing messages. With the rising cost of advertising and other promotional tools, the marketing objective of the company has evolved not only to control the expenses but also to confirm superiority over the competitors. To create the edge over the competitors, the companies are adopting effective brand strategy for new products and also redesign its old brand strategy. Therefore, to be unbeaten in the markets, both in national and international level, the marketing organizations must create, redesign and protect its brand so that the company will prosper in the long run. It is the marketing communication which ideally has positioned and presented a brand to people. Keeping it in mind, an effort would be there to provide an in depth study on how marketing communication manages to ascertain relationship with the customers. This study is based on various models that have proven how marketing communication has developed as an apparently integral part of the marketing and corporate communication strategies of many companies. The present study would also highlights how the messages are to be disseminated effectively to make the brand remain in the mind of the customers for longer time.

Key Words: *Communication Mix, Marketing Messages, Brand Building, FMCG Product, Customer Perception.*

Introduction:

The term marketing is an integral part of the company's business. It includes both producer and the consumers. It does not mean one way communication process rather it focuses on the exchange of values and ideas between consumers and producers. The concept of marketing originates in the beginning of the Twentieth century and had become a keystone-philosophy in the mid-fifties. In the sixties the marketing concept was regarded as the savior of companies. In contrary it remained unresponsive to greater societal issues in the seventies. The over segmentation creates discontentment in the eighties since customer needs were given too much priority (Morgan, 1996). In the twenty first century, marketing communication has given the requisite emphasis to survive in the competitive era and to get an edge over the competitors (Hackley, Kitchen, 1998). Thus to state specifically the term Marketing communication (MC) concept is derived from marketing management itself. This concept involves the coordination and integration among all marketing communication tools, avenues, and sources within a company. This concept is developed to make all the tools, avenues and sources to work as a unified force. This unified force has a definite impact on all of a firm's business, marketing channels, potential customers and internally directed communications to develop the brand awareness.

Marketing communication process incorporates all marketing tools, approaches, and resources within a company not only to establish a greater impact on consumer mind but also to generate maximum profit at minimum cost. Thus all the promotional tools need to be put together to gain competitive edge over competitor.

The marketing communication approach focuses to evolve brand awareness, deliver information, educate the market, and develop a positive image of the product brand. The objectives of MC are thus to measure the impact on the customers and the benefits they draw from it. Shimps (2000) has foretold that the objectives of the company and the benefits of the customer are two sides of the same coin since the main element behind MC is to start with the customer.

Table: 1 The framework for company objectives and customer benefits

Company Objective	Customer Benefit
Increase sales	Affect Behavior
Maintain or improve market share	Start with the customer
Create or improve Brand Recognition	Use any and all forms of contract
Create a favourable climate for future sales	Achieve Synergy
Improve promotional efficiency	Build Relationship

Source: Adapted from Belch and Belch (2001) and Shimps (2000)

Marketing Communication can only be effective if the message is delivered in a right channel in a right manner. The structure and execution of messages are the indispensable aspect of marketing communication.

Table: 2 The framework for message structure and message execution

Message Structure	Message Execution
Order of Presentation	Straight sell or Factual Message
Conclusion Drawing	Scientific / Technical
Message Sidedness	Demonstration
Refutation	Comparison
Verbal versus Visual Image	Testimonials
	Slice of Life
	Animation
	Personality
	Fantasy
	Dramatisation
	Humour
	Combination

Source: Adapted from Belch and Belch (2001)

The purpose of discussing marketing communication is to consider how effectively the tools are used by the companies considering the preference of the customers. Classic tools have its own strengths and limitations but not ignoring Internet which has already emerged as one of the most effective tool. New modern technology plays a major part of MC and the Internet in

particular since it can be appeared as both a tool and a media. The Internet according to Belch, Belch, (2001) is effective both from the company and the customer point of view.

Table: 3 The framework for the classic tools and Internet objectives

The Classical Tools	Internet Objectives
Advertising	Disseminate Information
Public Relation	Create Awareness
Sales Promotion	Gather Research Information
Direct Response	Create an Image
Personal Sales	Simulate Trial
Events and Sponsorships	Improve Customer Service
	Increase Distribution

Source: Adapted from Duncan (2002) and Belch and Belch (2001)

Literature Review:

The literature reviews provides a theoretical outline. It explores how marketing communication establishes a strong bond between potential customers and the product. Moreover, it establishes how marketing communication by disseminating messages helps to evolve as Brand.

According to Idman (1993), successful marketing communication has three obstacles to overcome. Firstly, the message should be delivered in a way that the audience must notice it. Next, the full attention of the audience has to be grabbed by framing the message in such a way as to make them understand all about it. Lastly, it is of utmost necessity to create certain feelings and atmospheres in order to awake wanted visions or patterns of behaviour.

Rowley (1998) has suggested that the marketing communications aim to increase sales, maintain or improve market share or create a competitive advantage. To reach these objectives different communication channels are used to convey the organizations message, with the help of different promotional tools such as advertising, personal selling, public relations, sales promotions and direct marketing.

Shimp (2000) has proposed Marketing communications as the collection of all elements in a brand's marketing mix to facilitate the exchanges through establish shared meaning with the brand's customers or clients. He has further stated that marketing communications is all about the organizations making sure that customer are aware of the products that the organizations offer.

Belch (2001) has evaluated that the objectives of marketing communications is manifold.. The primary focus is to allow more customers to buy the product or service, or get existing customers to buy more. He has also suggested to pay heed in the matter like Maintain or improving market share.

As per Reid (2005), *many* companies have adapted marketing communication to survive in the competitive marketing environment of today and increased managerial expectations related to marketing and thereby improve the management and integration of their marketing communications program. (Reid et al, 2005)

More recently, Yin Wong and Merriles (2007) have stated that the development of brands on an international arena offers opportunities to exploit economics of scale. They concluded that

branding is not the only parameter for succeeding on the global market. A firm may be a great marketer in one country, but the brand cannot literally be transferred to another country with the expectation of the brand becoming a success.

Keller (2008) has suggested that the role of brands within companies has changed over the last decades. The rising position of brands within companies implicates the need to understand how to manage the brand governance mechanisms effectively in order to maximize brand value and therewith also the company's profit (Bauer et al., 2000; Keller, 2008).

Guthrie & Kim, (2009) have pointed out the fact that *Brand Involvement* is a motivational state that can be used to understand consumer attitudes towards products or brands. They also have explained that Brand Involvement can also be framed as an analytical tool to measure the level of brand interest as well as the brand's significance to the consumer (Guthrie & Kim, 2009).

Park (2010) has assessed that consumers' self-construal has to be taken into account while analyzing the effects of brand personality on brand image,. The self-perception and the way consumers value their self-personalities also has an influence over the selection of the brand. (Park & John, 2010).

Freling, Crosno & Henard, (2011) have stated that Brand personality can be evaluated through the dimensions of brand personality appeal (BPA): favourability, originality and clarity. These three dimensions are extremely important in developing brand personality and their optimization leads to higher levels of consumer purchase intentions.

Objective of the Study:

Brands in FMCG have been specifically referred to a meaning to consumers, and these meanings can be acknowledged in part from experience. It is the marketing Communication which ideally has positioned and presented a FMCG brand to people. It is again the Marketing communication which helps to explore the brand in the market. This can only be possible by employing marketing communication tools aptly. This is why Marketing Communication is so vital and indispensable to develop brand awareness. The specific objectives of the study are:

- i. To provide an in depth study on how marketing communication manages to establish relationship with the customers.
- ii. To prove how marketing communication has become an integral part of corporate strategy by employing various models.
- iii. To ascertain how messages can be delivered aptly.

Models Used To Develop Brand Recognition Through Marketing Communication:

Marketing Communication is the collection of all elements in a brand's marketing mix. It facilitates exchanges by establishing shared meaning with the brand's customers or clients. Marketing Communication is the process employed by the marketers to make the customers aware of the product or services. It is even employed to achieve the organizational objectives. It even aims to increase sales, maintain or improve market share and to gain competitive advantage over others.

Communication Mix

Marketing Communication is a management concept. Its objective is to disseminate the message successfully to its target audience. Marketing communication is divided into several separate communication tools. These tools are employed to serve manifold purposes. The most likely contribution is to communicate with its target groups effectively or how the message can be transmitted to the target audience. As each tool has its own advantages and disadvantages, marketers usually prefer to use mix of these tools to make the entire process effective. (De Pelsmacker et al. 2007) The contribution of each marketing communication tools varies depending on the changing marketing environment, and thus marketers need to adjust their tools on the basis of the current scenario. (De Pelsmacker et al. 2007) The most common and convincing conventional approach is to distinguish marketing communication tools into the following categories: public relations, advertising, sales promotion, and personal selling. (Pickton & Broderick 2004) Direct marketing, exhibitions, or sponsoring fits are also among the necessary marketing tools. The newest tools which give marketing communication a different dimension is e-communication, which is also effective to stimulate purchasing. Word of mouth (WOM), is also in the hunt among the probable marketing communication tools. Duncan (2002) has listed different tools or functions such as advertising, public relations, sales promotion, the personal connection (direct response and personal sales) and experimental contacts (events and sponsorship). While implementing Marketing Communication, the strategy needs to be framed accordingly about the usage to make the promotional purpose effective in order to create the brand awareness & to help ultimately in creating customer relationship

Model 1: Consistent and Inconsistent Source of Message

Media is used specifically to inform the target market aptly. In advertising campaign of product only the main features along with USP (Unique Selling Proposition) are highlighted. Further detailed information on the product is also provided through direct mailing, websites, telemarketing, brochures etc. Message should be consistent i.e. same message should be delivered repeatedly through different media. Design consistency refers to consistency in color, photographs and other visual elements and proper linkage among these elements. Design consistency makes the www.aarhat.com/ERJ/June 2016/VOL III/Issues II/Impact Factor:2.148 / 63

process cost effective as well as increasing the impact on the audience. This of utmost necessity since some unseen factors often proves to be decisive. This consistency helps to develop a definite view of the product in the mind of the audience. In today's marketing; purchase is the lengthy and complex process as this process involves different decision makers and influencers. Outlook of others and unanticipated situational factors play a significant role. A relevant knowledge about the product gives the potential customers an edge over the others. It gives them the choice even to go for the purchase. Thus the appropriate repeated message at the right time gives a base to the Brand and the awareness stimulates even in the purchasing decision.

Model 2: Four Essential Components of Marketing Mix

(www.audiologyonline.com)

Marketing communication involves all the essential four components of marketing mix - the product, price, distribution and marketing communications. Marketing research should keep a close look on market segmentation for the proper functioning of marketing mix to make the target audience aware about the product. When a product is designed considering the needs of clearly defined consumers' segment, price of the product is also to be taken care off. The appropriate distribution channels and the marketing communications must be structured accordingly to pay heed to the characteristics of the target segment. The instruments which support and give a shape to the marketing communication activities are integrated communication strategy and integrated communication plan. The integrated communication strategy is reflected in market positioning. It is based on the Objectives aimed by the company and on communication axis. The integrated communication plan is focused on choosing the specific components, taking into account their effective correlation in terms of optimizing costs.

Model 3: Eight Distinctive Features to Focus from Company Perspective

Source: Kotler and Pfoertsch, 2006

All the eight distinctive feature of the brand are emphasized in the outer circle of the brand functions. The core represents the functions and value for the consumer. In contrary the outer circle signifies how far these values develop the unique status for the company. All the features are interrelated and thus help to achieve the desired result. Brand preference is achieved by delivering the perceived promise .The effective differentiated marketing manages to create a brand image in the mind of the customers. Thus the brand manages to develop the brand loyalty in the mind of the target market and as a result the potential customers would show their eagerness to pay the extra premium for its distinctiveness. Again it gives the opportunity to the company to improve its market share. Again, the eight brand features situated in the outer circle of the brand functions represents the core functions and value for the consumer. These roles are linked to each other and thus responsible for developing an edge over the competitors. As a result of that loyalty towards the brand, it will secure future business and increase brand equity in a sustainable manner (Kotler and Pfoertsch, 2006).

Model 4: Three Elementary factors of Assessment

Source: Elements of corporate branding (Hatch & Schultz 2003).

This model focuses on three factors - management, employees and external stakeholders. Vision refers to the aspiration of the top management. They have to consider the objectives as well to achieve in the future. The employees are the integral part of the strategic planning. Thus their active participation holds the key for the success. They are the one to represent the organizational culture. Image refers to the impression the stake holders have for the organization. Their consideration and views are the most valuable point to assess.

Model 5: Sequence of Brand Building Process

Source: Brand building process (adapted from Kotler & Pfoertsch 2006)

Kotler and Pfoertsch (2006) see brand building as a sequence of processes. At first, brand planning takes place. The framework for the brand is developed by coordinating several internal processes and procedures. This is framed to give a proper shape to brand orientation. Second, brand analysis needs to be done. It can only be possible by considering brand mission, personality and brand values. All these attributes need to be aligned with the corporate vision and mission. Management and employees responsible for the brand awareness activities need to take into account the key attributes of the products and services of the company. They need to understand and anticipate the needs of their customers and other stakeholder groups. The third steps include development of Brand Strategy. It is entirely depended on the core value and association of the brand. Brand architecture relates corporate or product brand only by understanding the target market. In Fourth step, brand implementation is to be done. Here attention is given to implement the plan. Fifth, and last, brand audit is performed. It controls and evaluates the performance of the established brand. Thus Brand building makes its presence felt. It is being done not only by distinguishing it but also by establishing a strong brand image on the mind of the customers.

Model 6: Key Aspects and Factors to Consider in Marketing Mix

Marketing Communication always plays a vital role to establish the brand. To develop the Brand, marketing Communication tools need to be employed effectively. Before employing the media mix, key aspects need to be considered. The tangible and intangible attributes need to evolve out along with the product function, benefit and operation. It needs to be cleared to whom the message is to be delivered along with geographical segmentation, culture and competition. Based on all these, the message is to be framed and the right media vehicles are to be opted to make the message transmitted effectively. Only by systematically employing this mix, the information delivered would bring an effect on the potential customers.

How Marketing Communication Tools Be Employed To Develop Brand Awareness:

The marketers are using various marketing communication tools in creating brand relationship in FMCG. Brand relationship in FMCG gives the option to develop Brand Awareness. Brand awareness again plays a vital role in consumer decision making process. These are learning, consideration and choice. Brand awareness is the result of consumer's exposure to brand. Brand awareness in FMCG refers to the ability by which the customer recognizes the Brand. Brand awareness stands for both brand recognition and recall. Brand awareness is nothing but the ability of the potential buyer to recognize and recall a brand in respect of a certain product category. One of the advantages of marketing communication tools is the ability to reach consumers of FMCG. The consumers search for the information which is being provided by the marketing communication tools. This information can be disseminated properly only by assessing the target audience properly. Considering their choice, the messages are to be delivered aptly and consistently by various communication tools. This regular and consistent information develops a bonding between brand and the customers. This bonding generates a perception which in return helps to develop Brand awareness in the mind of the customers by making them knowledgeable about the product attributes. This positive effect would help the customers to identify a definite brand from the product cue. Again marketers use various communication tools to develop brand awareness to retain the product's current customer base and to cement relationship with them too.

Conclusion:

Marketing Communication helps to disseminate the information. It can only be done by assessing the target market properly. In response to the assessment, different promotional tools need to be employed to ensure the reach. To incorporate all in a positive note, only opens up the avenue to reach the message successfully in the mind of the consumer. Moreover, it helps the message to have an ever lasting impression in the mind of the customers for a long time. This impression through promotional tools helps to develop the brand awareness in the mind of the customers. The brand awareness instigates the customers to select the desirable brand from the product cues. In a nutshell, marketing communication tools entice the customers to develop a definite bonding with the Brand.

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